

Article Title:
Resistance of Leech and Insects against Cold and Freezing

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Abstract

Individuals who, in their daily lives, deal with cold environments and refrigeration equipment (such as mountaineers) are exposed to many dangers resulting from freezing and the incompatibility of the human body with cold. If the human body temperature in the cold drops below 29.5 degrees Celsius, the human heart, instead of 60 beats, beats once or twice per minute, and blood cannot be pumped fast enough to the body, which eventually leads to a calm death.

In the experiments, attempts were made to choose an animal that has enzymes resistant to cold so that we can find a strong anti-cold agent.

Research Topic: Resistance of Leech and Insects against Cold and Freezing

Keywords: Refrigeration, Calm Death, Anti-Cold, Leech

Introduction

Humans have always sought health, and in this regard, they have tried to make the best use of available facilities and materials. Many people in society spend hours of their days in cold places or deal with refrigeration equipment. Naturally, these individuals are exposed to many dangers.

Our metabolism provides the necessary nutrients for the body. With this system, the metabolism of nutrients is broken down and digested to the extent that cells can use them. Metabolism in cold air requires more energy. When the weather is cold, blood vessels constrict so that the body does not lose too much of its heat. As a result of freezing, ice crystals form in the tissues of the organs of the body, which damage the cells of these tissues. When organs do not receive enough blood, they become thin and fragile, and the body starts to ache. At first, the fingers of the hands and feet, nose, and ears start to hurt. When the body temperature drops further, then it is the turn of the vital organs of the body such as the heart, lungs, and brain. If the body temperature drops only two degrees below normal, *hypothermia*² is spoken of, and the body begins to shiver. When the body temperature reaches 32 degrees Celsius, then the shivering of the body calms down—in fact, the body no longer has the energy to shiver; afterwards, we become confused and dazed. When the body temperature drops below 29.5 degrees Celsius, the person becomes unconscious, and the heart works less, and instead of 60 beats, it beats once or twice per minute, and as a result, death occurs.

I want to investigate whether in the body of some animals there exists a substance that prevents them from freezing up to a certain temperature, and in this regard, I used Spider, stink bug (*Eurygaster Integriceps*), and leech.

Leech: A type of annelid worm. The leech is an animal from the group of aquatic worms and belongs to the order Arhynchobdellida. The leech has 3 jaws and each jaw has 100 teeth; that is, the leech has about 300 extremely tiny teeth.

Most leeches live around freshwater, while some species can be found in soil and also around seas.

Stink Bug (*Eurygaster Integriceps*): Belongs to the family of true bugs and the order Hemiptera, and is considered one of the very important pests.

Spider: An invertebrate predator that has a two-part body and eight legs and belongs to the phylum Arthropoda.

Then I prepared the samples and placed them in the freezer and measured the freezing time.

2. hypothermia

The leech was able to revive after 45 minutes at -18°C and then 20 minutes at room temperature (25°C).

Research Method

In this research, the experimental method has been used, which includes independent, dependent, and control variables. In this research, we reach the real goal through experimentation.

Materials Required and Method of Work

1. Glass plate
2. Leech
3. Stink Bug
4. Oak worm
5. Spider
6. Analog hygrometer
7. Latex gloves
8. Disposable gloves
9. Freezer
10. Metal forceps
11. Small plastic bottle
12. Digital thermometer

Steps

- * First, I set the freezer temperature to -18°C , then removed the leech from the water and placed it in a small plastic bottle.
- * I placed this leech in the freezer at intervals of 10 minutes, 15 minutes, 20 minutes, 25 minutes, 30 minutes, 35 minutes, and 45 minutes, and after a while, it revived. But at 50 minutes, unfortunately, the leech did not revive.
- * Next, it was the spider's turn. I placed it in a glass plate and put it in the freezer at intervals of 10 minutes, 15 minutes, 20 minutes, and 25 minutes, and after a while, it revived. But at 26 minutes it did not revive.
- * Then it was the turn of the insect called the stink bug (Maura), which is a type of plant pest. I placed it in a glass plate and put it in the freezer for 10 minutes and 15 minutes, and after a while, it revived.

It should be noted that this insect, at 20 minutes, revived after 12 hours. But it lived only 3 hours and then died.

Table of Reviving Time of Samples after Freezing (in Minutes)

Explanation: As indicated in the table, in the experiments conducted, the revival of the samples was measured based on time, and the following data show the revival of the samples after freezing. According to the data, the leech could survive the longest at -18°C .

Samples	Minutes
Leech	45
Spider	25
Stink Bug	15

Reviving Time Chart of Samples after Freezing

Explanation: On one side of the chart above, the experimental samples (leech, spider, stink bug) are shown, and on the other side, the last reviving time of the samples is shown based on time (minutes).

Discussion and Conclusion

The results obtained from the experiments on the samples showed that the leech, more than all the other samples, can withstand -18°C and survive, and the Stink Bug, which is a type of pest, was able to endure 15 minutes in the freezer. This itself can be a reason for using genetic science to modify the genome of the Stink Bug so that it becomes vulnerable to cold, and farmers can achieve more economic yield from their products.

But the interesting point in this experiment was the spider's method of protecting itself, in such a way that by spinning a web it was able to withstand -18°C for 25 minutes. Therefore, in this research, we concluded that the Almighty God chooses various methods for the protection of His creatures from the cold.

Suggestions

- Investigating what substance exists inside the leech that increases its resistance to freezing, so that in laboratories we can reach its compounds and use them in the form of cream, ampoule, or pill for mountaineers, divers, and people exposed to freezing.
- Using genetic science, transferring that antifreeze substance that exists in the leech to other animals.
- Preparing a thin and resistant clothing from the combination of spider web and nanocarbon for the protection of human bodies, or preparing a coating to preserve food against freezing.

— Investigating the compounds of leech blood and simulating them with humans and other creatures for injection and strengthening of their bodies against cold.

References:

1. *Canon of Medicine*. Avicenna, Vol. 1, p. 495, Translated by Mr. Abdolrahman Sharafkandi
2. *Encyclopedia of Insects*. Alfred Lawrence Mond, Translated by Ms. Nasim Ahmadi
3. *The Wonderful World of Insects*. Translated by Mr. Habib Emami
4. *The First Atlas of Animals*. Translated by Mr. Hossein Alvandi
5. Leech – Wikipedia
6. Insects – Wikipedia
7. Worms – Wikipedia
8. Spider – Wikipedia
9. www.kharidezaloo.ir
10. www.articl.fspmarket.com